

ISic1188

I.Sicily inscription 1188

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, San Marco d'Alunzio

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140672

1. Διονύσωλ.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492794

EDCS 39101552

PHI 140672

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0365 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 194 no.7

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1188. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385574>